

AI Decision Support Tools in Food Systems:

A Horizon Scanning Report

Acknowledgements

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Contents

Executive Summary	4
Glossary of Terms	6
1. Background	7
2. Methods	9
3. Preliminary Results	13
4. Discussion	15
5. Limitations	18
6. Recommendations - From Horizon Scanning to Horizon Shaping	19
Conclusions	20
References	21

Executive summary

The aim of this research project is to investigate the current and future landscape of artificial intelligence (AI)-driven decision support tools within food systems, with particular focus on their application to local and regional food networks.

Working with FixOurFood and the Food Standards Agency, this report explores how AI technologies are being developed and deployed to address complex challenges in food procurement, safety, and supply chain management, examining whether these tools can effectively support the optimization of local food systems. Through comprehensive horizon scanning, this research seeks to understand the alignment between available AI capabilities and stakeholder needs, ultimately determining whether current technologies can adequately support the transition toward more efficient, sustainable, and locally integrated food systems that reduce waste, improve safety, and enhance regional food security.

Key Findings

There is a substantial disconnect between the capabilities of AI tools and the needs of local food system stakeholders. Current tools are predominantly vendor driven and designed for large scale industrial settings, making them inaccessible and perpetuating inequities for smaller-scale producers, local authorities and community-led food networks.

Three Horizons Analysis

1. **Horizon 1:** AI tools in use today often lack transparency, rely on high-quality data potentially reinforcing inequities.
2. **Horizon 2:** Emerging innovations should focus on adapting tools to smaller contexts and fostering openness in collaboration (gathering their perspectives and experience) between developers and stakeholders.
3. **Horizon 3:** Envisions community driven, AI systems that are inclusive, equitable, and empower local stakeholders through participatory design and tailored governance.

Critical Challenges

1. Insufficient data infrastructure, especially among smaller producers
2. Lack of transparency in AI decision making
3. Limited financial and technical resources for adequate adoption
4. Minimal stakeholder involvement in tool development

Executive summary

Strategic Implications

Current market-driven approaches need to be reoriented towards inclusive innovation

Recommendations

To address these challenges, this report recommends:

1. Developing inclusive innovation frameworks that mandate stakeholder engagement
2. Investing in accessible data infrastructure for smaller food systems
3. Establishing standardised guidelines for AI implementation in local contexts
4. Prioritising transparency and interpretability in AI design
5. Supporting community-led approaches to tool development.

Future research should focus on:

1. Comparative analysis across different food system contexts
2. Policy tools that enable adaptive, responsible innovation

Conclusion

This research provides a foundation for evidence-based decision making about AI adoption in local food systems while highlighting the importance of ensuring that technological advancement serves broader goals of food systems resilience, justice and sustainability.

Glossary of Terms

Artificial intelligence (AI): Systems capable of performing tasks that typically require human intelligence such as reasoning, learning from data, understanding natural language and perception.

Machine Learning (ML): Subset of AI that enables systems to learn from and make reductions or decisions based on data. ML algorithms improve their performance over time as they are exposed to more data, without needing to be programmed for each new task.

Black Box Models: Models, particularly deep neural networks, whose internal reasonings are not easily interpretable or explainable. While these modes can be highly efficient, their decision-making process can be opaque, creating issues with responsibility and traceability.

Interpretable models: These are modes designed to be transparent and explainable. Examples include decision trees and rule-based systems, where the logic behind decisions can be understood and traced.

Linear supply chain optimisation: The process of improving the efficiency and effectiveness of a supply chain by minimising waste, reducing costs, and maximising output through data-drive methods.

Circular value creation: sustainability-driven business model where waste or by-products are used as inputs or another recess, creating a circular flow of resources.

Decision support tools: Systems or software applications that help users make informed decisions by providing data analytics, predictive models, and recommendations.

Predictive analytics: The use of historical data, statistical algorithms and machine learning techniques to forecast future outcomes. Predictive analytics helps organisations anticipate trends, behaviours and to entail risks, allowing for more proactive decision making.

Digital Twins: Virtual representations of physical systems, objects or processes that use real-time data to simulate and predict the behaviour of their real-world counterparts.

Agri-Tech: digital agriculture that uses data technologies to improve sustainability by combining AI robotics, and biotechnology paired with global data on livestock, food species, disease state, soil conditions and weather patterns.¹

Food System: The food system encompasses all processes and infrastructure involved in feeding a population, including the production, processing, distribution, consumption and disposal of food, as well as the associated inputs and outputs. It also includes the socioeconomic and environmental contexts in which these activities occur.²

Supply Chain: The ability for goods and services to be produced and delivered to the right place, time and in the right quantity in a cost effective manner.

Resilience: The ability of a system to return to its original (or desired state) after being disturbed.

Supply chain management: The coordination of activities involved in sourcing, procurement, production, and logistics to deliver products from suppliers to end consumers while balancing cost, quality, speed, and sustainability.

1. Background

Food systems are under increasing pressure from climate change, population growth, resource constraints and shifting consumer demands.^{3,4} By 2050, feeding nearly 10 billion people will require transformative changes to ensure that everyone has access to sustainable food for all.⁵ This is coupled with inefficiencies including food waste, safety, supply chain disruptions, resource optimization challenges and inconsistent safety standards.

The convergence of AI in agriculture provides an opportunity to address these systemic challenges. AI technologies provide significant advantages by optimising crop cultivation practices, enabling the use of predicting modelling and precision agriculture techniques and streamlining efficient crop monitoring and disease identification.⁶ In addition to this, AI provides predictive analytics for demand and supply management, blockchain for transparency and traceability, and improves distribution efficiency via AI powered logistics.⁷

Local and regional food systems are often presented to have enhanced sustainability and resilience to globalised supply chains. This is due to their ability to strengthen local economies, reduce environmental impacts and improve food access. However, they also face unique challenges and vulnerabilities. Reliance on local food supply chains can create vulnerabilities in other ways. Concentrated local production can be severely disrupted by weather events. The challenges facing local food systems extend beyond climate vulnerabilities. Key challenges facing farmers are market disruptions, labour shortages, rising input costs and high energy prices.⁸ Small scale producers often lack robust data infrastructure, limiting their ability to make informed decisions about production distribution, and risk management.

The Yorkshire and Humber region face significant challenges within its food system, notably in the areas of food waste and supply chain stability. Each year (as of 2018) approximately 300,000 tonnes of food are discarded highlighting inefficiencies in production, distribution and consumption⁹. In addition to this, the region's food supply chains are increasingly vulnerable due to complex interdependencies and growing competition between food vendors.

As a result, these challenges require decision support tools that are capable of optimising procurement, distribution, safety monitoring and waste reduction in context-specific ways.

1. Background

1.1 What role does AI have in Food Systems?

These challenges could be addressed with AI. AI-based demand forecasting uses machine learning algorithms to analyse historical data, market trends, and external factors to predict future demand accurately, enabling retailers to work together to reduce waste and improve product availability.^{10,11} In regard to quality and safety monitoring, AI-driven inspection tools can identify contamination, assess quality and ensure compliance. AI algorithms can analyse visual data such as images or videos of food items from cameras to identify defects, contamination, or irregularities along the entire process, from packaging to delivery.¹² These systems enable real-time monitoring and early warnings, with AI enhancing compliance monitoring, reducing public health risks.¹³

In risk management, AI enhances system resilience by identifying and flagging emerging risks earlier than traditional methods. AI has effectively been applied to outbreak detection, allergen or spoilage issues.¹⁴ In regard to sustainability, AI can measure carbon footprints, optimise shelf life, and support circular economy models that reduce environmental impacts.¹⁵

The integration of AI technologies into food systems represents both an opportunity and necessity for building resilience, however successful implementation requires careful consideration of local contexts, and the specific vulnerabilities that different food systems face in a time of increasing environmental and economic uncertainty.

2. Methods

This study adopted a qualitative approach combining primary and secondary data collection methods to generate insights about the role of AI-driven decision support tools in food systems.

2.1 Literature review

A literature review was conducted to provide context for primary research findings and identify key themes in existing research. The review included 21 peer-reviewed articles, 2019-2025, focusing on AI applications in food systems, technology adoption in agriculture, and sustainable food system transformation. The articles selected are closely aligned to our research aims.

2.1.1 Inclusion criteria

Search strategies employed multiple databases and used combinations of terms including “artificial intelligence or AI” “machine learning or ML” “large language models or LLM” “decision support,” “food systems,” “resilient,” “local or regional,” “agriculture,” “local food,” “sustainable agriculture,” and “technology”.

2.1.2 Horizon 1: Current AI applications

Current AI decision support tools in the food system demonstrate potential for high performance capabilities but face significant accessibility challenges. These systems are often opaque, heavily dependent on high-quality data and vendor-driven, which alienates small scale farmers and reinforces existing inequities (Bronson, 2018).¹⁶ An assessment is needed to determine whether local food systems have necessary resources to adopt AI driven decision support tools.

Key applications

Demand forecasting and waste reduction: Machine learning models are showing significant success in reducing food waste through improved demand forecasting. Mu et al (2024) identified AI development in demand forecasting as crucial for enhancing food system resilience through proactive food safety management.¹⁷ Real world implementations demonstrate substantial impact: Rodrigues et al (2024) found that machine learning models (Random Forest and LSTM) reduced food waste by 14-52% compared to traditional forecasting in institutional settings like student canteens and company cafeterias.¹⁸ In addition to this, Hubner et al (2024) evaluated Foodforecast, a cloud-based machine learning service for bakeries, which achieved a 30% reduction in product returns, with environmental gains outweighing the AI's systems footprint by 1-3 times.¹⁹

2. Methods

Food Safety Enhancement: Dhal and Kar (2025) demonstrate that AI enhances food safety through multiple mechanisms: real time contamination detection, predictive modelling for risk assessment, compliance monitoring systems, automated defect detection, optimised shelf-life predictions and consistency assurance.²⁰ However, Dimitrakopoulou and Garre (2025) emphasise that AI's effectiveness in food safety is "only as strong as the data that feeds it," highlighting the critical importance of robust data infrastructure and collaborative development designs.²¹

Supply Chain Risk Prediction: Baryannis et al. (2019) proposed machine learning frameworks for predicting supply chain risks, particularly delivery delays, while balancing model performance with interpretability.²² Their research comparing black box models with interpretable models shows that while complex models achieve higher precision, interpretable models provide actionable insights for stakeholders. This enables more informed decision-making and enhances trust in AI-driven recommendations which is crucial for adoption among farmers and local authorities.

Food Waste Management: Clark et al. (2025) explore AI driven food waste management from hospitality industry applications like smart bin vendors (Leanpath and Winnow) that can be scaled down for household settings.²³ Cincullo et al (2022) examined 41 startups using big data for food waste reduction, categorising approaches into linear supply chain optimisation and circular value creation.²⁴

2.1.3 Horizon 2: Transitional Innovations

This horizon is focused on bridging the gap between AI and real-world adoption. These innovations are designed to be implementable for local food systems. This section addresses the practical challenges around adoption, usability, trust and equity.

Current systems require high quality data inputs that may not be available in local and regional contexts creating a significant barrier to adoption. There are also transparency and trust issues. Kovari (2024) highlights the critical balance needed between accuracy, transparency, and trust in AI decision support systems.²⁵ The "black box" nature of many AI tools creates resistance among end users such as farmers, policy makers, and supply chain managers who need to understand and trust AI-generated insights. As mentioned above, interpretable models may sacrifice some precision but provide actionable insights that build stakeholder trust.

2. Methods

Furthermore, there are vendor and equity concerns that need addressing. Bronson (2018) argues that while big data driven tools promise productivity, they often centre the value of developers rather than small scale farmers. Consequently, this results in unequal access to data, lack of farmer agency/autonomy, insufficient customisation for small scale operations, and vendor-controlled tools that do not holistically serve diverse community needs.¹⁸

Lastly, current deployment shows significant gaps in accessibility for both public and private sector food safety management (Mu et al., 2024). The resource requirements for AI implementation may not be compatible with resource-constrained local food systems which calls for adaptation and further support.¹⁷

In order to move forward towards Horizon 3, there needs to be a development of partnerships with farmers and local authorities to co-design AI tools that meet actual user needs. In doing so, we advocate for “rights holders” such as farmers, marginalised stakeholders and communities, into the innovation process as co-creators rather than passive recipients.

In terms of data ownership and governance, local ownership and control of AI tools and data with clear frameworks for data sharing are needed. This requires capacity building and support which includes developing resources, training and technical support systems to effective access and implementation.

2.1.4 Horizon 3: Transformative Futures

This horizon focused on visionary, long term innovations that aim to reshape existing governance, values, agency and systems surrounding AI, encouraging a collaborative approach with a community framework.

A just and resilient system that:

1. Provides accessible AI tools to all communities and small-scale farmers
2. Ensures meaningful stakeholder participation in system design and governance, with rights holders and co-creators
3. Eliminates barriers that currently exclude smaller operators through appropriate scaling and support
4. Balances technological capabilities with transparency and interpretability needs
5. Establishes equitable data governance frameworks that serve community interest
6. Integrates proactive risk management across all scales of the food system.

2. Methods

2.2 Primary Data: Stakeholder Interviews

Semi-structured interviews were conducted using a prepared interview guide to capture stakeholder perspectives on the opportunities, barriers and needs around AI decision support tools.

1. Sampling and recruitment: Invitations were sent to 20 stakeholders across the categories of delivery and logistics, supermarkets and distributors, food production, developers, regulators and end users.
2. Questions were generated and peer reviewed tailored to each interviewee. These questions explored their current awareness and use of AI within their organisation, problems they would like to address using AI, current barriers to their adoption of AI as well as their views on transparency, equity and governance.
3. Interviews conducted: 4 interviews were completed virtually lasting 30 minutes -1 hour.
4. Interview transcripts were then thematically analysed to identify recurring themes and triangulated with findings from the literature review.

Thematic analysis proceeded through six phases:

1. Data familiarisation
2. Initial coding
3. Coding development and refinement
4. Theme construction and refinement
5. Theme definition

Ethical considerations

Informed consent was obtained from all participants, with assurance of de-identification and withdrawal rights, within the FixOurFood research programme.

2.3 Secondary data: Global survey

To generate a broader understanding, a short survey was generated to gather global insights (USA, EU) on AI adoption in food systems. This survey was sent to 22 vendors across the following categories: research development and regional innovation hubs, data analytics and robotics, precision agriculture and farm operations, supermarket, retail and consumer facing food tech and delivery and logistics.

3. Preliminary Results

Table 1 presents the preliminary thematic analysis results, displaying the main themes and codes identified from stakeholder interviews.

Theme	Code
Data Ownership as a Barrier to AI Adoption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data as a proprietary asset Operational data as a competitive advantage Reluctance to participate in collective AI initiatives that could benefit the broader food system Cybersecurity vulnerabilities Sharing of data seen as a barrier
Sustainability as Contested and Undefined	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of consensus around sustainability definitions Multiple dimensions (financial, environmental etc.) with unclear relationships Multiplicity creates challenges for AI system developers who need clear parameters and success metrics Without clear definitions, AI tools risk optimising narrow metrics that may undermine broader sustainability goals
Communication Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Disconnect between technical/academic sustainability frameworks and farm level realities Need to translate between AI developers and farming communities
Technology Adoption Paradox	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Significant investments in data generation technologies (sensors, monitoring systems) without utilisation capabilities Data generation-utilisation gap (inability to extract actionable insights) Legacy system integration challenges- challenges integrating new AI technologies with existing operational systems Non-linear tech adoption patterns
Overlapping Disruptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Simultaneous pressures: climate impacts, policy changes, financial instability, uncertain government support Overlapping disruptions can create complex decision-making environments where simple AI optimisation models may prove inadequate

3. Preliminary Results

Figure 1: The food system framework developed by Foresight4Food (<https://foresight4food.net/food-systems-model/>) This framework has been edited to highlight the key areas where AI demonstrates influence within food systems.²⁶

4. Discussion

“I can’t see, in 5 years, how hardly anything in the food sector isn’t going to be touched by it (AI).”

This research highlights a paradox within food systems, where there is substantial investment in data generation but limited capacity for meaningful data utilisation. This “investment without integration” challenges conventional technology adoption models and suggests that successful AI implementations require more than technological capacity alone.

The findings indicate that while stakeholders recognise AI’s potential for addressing critical challenges such as waste reduction, supply chain optimisation, and improving food safety, the reality of implementation is constrained by structural barriers, rather than technological limitations.

4.1 AI integration into Regional Food System Governance

The interviews provided critical insights about regional food system governance - how there is a governance gap where food resilience receives little regulatory attention. One participant noted a “lack of emphasis on food (in emergency planning)... we take it from an economic point of view”. There is a low prioritisation of food in resilience forums, despite COVID-19 exposing system vulnerabilities.

As a result, this suggests that the institutional foundations necessary for effective AI integration remain underdeveloped. This finding was reinforced by other participants, who reported efforts as large voluntary and economically framed rather than regulatory requirements.

Even though this gap creates space for AI solutions, it also raises fundamental questions about whether technological fixes can adequately address structural governance deficiencies.

4.1.1 Data Governance and Trust as Critical Barriers

Data ownership emerged as the most fundamental barrier to AI adoption, revealing tensions between competitive interests of food companies and collective benefits. One participant shared concerns about data “being used by bad actors” as this could have a “detrimental effect on supply chains”. Data governance is a challenge that runs deeper than technological solutions and is more rooted in the imbalances of trust, power and value distribution within food systems.

These tensions manifest across different power relationships within the food system. Concerns about data scope, sharing and sensitivity of farm operations, exemplify how data governance challenges extend beyond individual farm level privacy to encompass broader questions of market power and control. The tension between the need for collaborative data sharing and competitive commercial interests represents a fundamental structural barrier that technological solutions alone cannot resolve.

Trusting in AI systems presents additional challenges. There was a particular concern with large language models “hallucinating” and providing incorrect information, which inadvertently affects the reliability of these technological applications. In food safety contexts, where errors can have serious public health consequences, these reliability concerns become critical barriers to adoption.

4. Discussion

Data privacy concerns were also noted. Farmers can be protective and concerned that their data could be exposed commercially and overlooked by AI. In conjunction with this, privacy concerns were compounded by cybersecurity risks, with participants noting that AI systems could be “used by bad actors [...] detrimental impacts on supply chains”. This concern is echoed in policy contexts, where stakeholders see this as a significant risk requiring regulatory attention.

Current market driven approaches to AI deployment inadequately address the collaborative data sharing necessary for effective local food system optimisation. This individualistic approach needs reframing to make AI decision support tools most effective for regional system resilience.

4.2 Environmental tensions

Participants expressed significant concerns about the environmental implications of AI infrastructure, particularly regarding water consumption needed for data centres and the potential use of agricultural lands for data centre siting. Without adequate consideration, AI decision support tools could undermine the agricultural systems they aim to protect.

These concerns align with border policy recognition of “land use trade foods for data centres vs. agricultural land” and “potential competition with agricultural and human needs, especially during droughts”. The high water and energy demands of AI infrastructure create direct competition with agricultural resources - particularly problematic in a context where participants noted concerns about “soaring utility bills” affecting farm viability.

The environmental tensions reveal a broader contradiction in AI adoption for sustainability: while AI promises to optimise resource use and reduce waste in food systems, its infrastructure requirements may exacerbate the environmental pressures it aims to address.

4.3 AI as a Tool for Regional Food System Monitoring and Co-ordination

Results show the potential for AI to improve traceability and prevent human error, with capabilities that directly address food safety concerns while potentially reducing regulatory burden through automated compliance monitoring. Stakeholders identified specific applications including real time awareness of availability, production, and risk and enhanced traceability and fraud detections. This could address incidents like “mislabelling or horsemeat type incidents”.

While there is recognition of AI’s value to “inventory and distribution optimization” and emerging applications like “autonomous tractors, land quality tools, and crop/field planners” the reality is that end user (farmer) AI app costs are marginal; the major cost/constraint lies in national-scale data centre energy. This reinforces the findings that barriers are structural and infrastructural rather than technological or financial at the point of use.

The emphasis on maintaining human authority in decision-making processes remains critical for addressing transparency and accountability challenges. As one participant noted, this helps ensure someone remains accountable for the consequences of decisions, addressing concerns about algorithmic decision making in contexts with significant public health and economic implications.

Current applications focus on efficiency and optimization, with “fewer manual roles, more automation in advanced manufacturing” expected as trends continue. However, the transition to more automated applications depends on resolving the structural barriers identified rather than simply advancing the technology.

4. Discussion

4.4 Skills Gaps

Stakeholders consistently identified skills shortages as a critical barrier, with needs spanning “AI knowledge and its application to the food system” requiring “more interdisciplinary expertise so AI capabilities and food system knowledge can be bridged”.

This skills gap extends across the entire food system. Participants identified “skills shortage across farmers, producers, processors and retailers” creating risks of both premature or ineffective adoption and conversely, that “delayed adoption risks falling behind other sectors”.

This challenge extends beyond technological skills to encompass an understanding of food system complexities and governance structures. The need for interdisciplinary expertise reflects the reality that effective AI implementation requires integration of both technological capabilities and deep disciplinary knowledge across multiple levels of the food system.

4.5 Regulatory Adaptation and Governance Innovation

The findings reveal a need for new approaches to governance that can adapt to rapid technological change while addressing structural food system challenges. Regional authorities emphasise the needs for “flexible mechanisms and collaborations rather than prescriptive, quickly outdated rules”.

This adaptive approach acknowledges the limits of forecasting in a fast-moving technological landscape, while recognising that regulatory frameworks must evolve to address emerging risks. Stakeholders call for “regular, sector-specific guidance on AI’s evolving role in food safety, resilience, and procurements” with periodic updates detailing developments to support informed, proportionate responses.

Stakeholders recognised the plausibility of a future AI-related incident in food systems and therefore mentioned the need for proactive governance approaches that can prevent rather than merely respond to technological disruptions.

5. Limitations:

Sample size and seasonal constraints:

The limited number of interviews, constraints the generalisability of these findings. Due to the season the research was conducted, many potential participants were unavailable, creating additional barriers to recruitment.

Temporal constraints:

The rapid pace of AI development means that current findings may quickly become outdated. The research captures current AI capabilities and adoption, but this could change significantly in the future

6. Recommendations:

From Horizon Scanning to Horizon Shaping

“The priority needs to be key safety challenges... food safety is probably one of the biggest.”

The findings reveal that effective AI integration in the food system requires co-ordinated interventions addressing structural barriers rather than technological limitations.

6.1 Adaptive Governance and Regulatory Framework Development

1. Establish sector-specific AI guidance frameworks that provide regular updates synthesising technological developments and their implications for food safety, resilience, and procurement.
2. Prioritise regulatory attention where risks are most acute: food safety, cybersecurity and data protection.

6.2: Data Governance and Trust Infrastructure

1. Implement pilot programs demonstrating collective data sharing benefits without compromising individual stakeholder autonomy.
2. Develop regional data trusts or similar institutional arrangements that enable data sharing while protecting competitive interests and privacy concerns.
3. Create transparency mechanisms that build trust in AI systems through auditable decision making processes.

6.3 Skills Development and Capacity Building

1. Create peer learning networks that enable smaller stakeholders to share AI knowledge and resources.
2. Develop training programs specifically designed for food system contexts, moving beyond generic AI education.
3. Establish regional AI expertise hubs which can support multiple food system organisations with interdisciplinary teams combining AI and food system expertise.

6.4 Infrastructure Development and Environmental Integration

1. Create incentives for AI infrastructure developments that provide direct benefits to local food system.
2. Develop regional planning frameworks that consider AI infrastructure needs alongside agricultural land use and food security objectives.

6.5 Designing for System Heterogeneity

1. Rather than uniform adoption patterns, AI systems should account for the significant heterogeneity in stakeholder needs, capabilities and contexts.

7: Conclusions

This research reveals that realising AI's transformative potential for food system resilience requires moving towards understanding technology as a complex web of interactions between human and non-human actors.

The findings suggest that effective AI integration demands re-imagining technology as a collaborative, equity focused process that dismantles structural barriers while establishing robust institutional foundations for sustainable implementation. Current government policies can be focused heavily on quantitative metrics, failing to capture diverse voices and perspectives essential for understanding AI's emerging social and ethical implications in food systems.

Therefore, the path forward requires technological innovation that is inclusive, transparent and backed by adaptive governance frameworks.

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